

QUALITY MANAGEMENT (TQM) IN IMPROVING MADRASAH TSANAWIYAH AN NUR 1 MALANGBONG GARUT DISTRICT

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Abstract

In the process of improving the quality of human resources, attention to quality is very important. The goals of National Education will be realized through two main things: first, through the formation of high-quality and independent human beings. Second, human resources and material resources are needed. Total Quality Management (TQM) in MTs. Annur 1 Malangbong Garut. This study took a qualitative descriptive method. Based on this research, it is known that the success of quality improvement through the implementation of Total Quality Management is inseparable from the focus on customers, continuous improvement, and total involvement of all stakeholders. MTs. Annur 1 Malangbong Garut provides the best service based on reliability, responsiveness, empathy, and certainty, with its strategic planning and excellent service as a priority to bring customers (especially teachers and employees) to a high level of satisfaction and loyalty.

Keywords: Total Quality Management, Development Quality

A. PRELIMINARY

For companies/organizations wishing to take part in a competitive competition for profit/benefit, there is no other way but to implement Total Quality Management. Philip Kolter (1994) says: Quality is our best assurance of customer allegiance, our strongest defense against foreign competition, and the only path to sustainable growth and earnings.

Likewise, quality can be applied in the world of education. Edward Salis (2008:21) argues that the application of TQM, which was previously used in the industrial world, does not mean that business methods are superior to educational applications, more than that, the business world can learn from the methods applied in various schools, colleges, and universities.

Improving the quality of education itself is an integrated process of improving the quality of human resources. Realizing the importance of improving the quality of human resources, the government issued Law no. 22 of 1999 concerning regional governments that give authority to regions to carry out regional autonomy to bring about changes in the management and implementation of education. In line with this, Law no. 20 of 2003 concerning the national education system in chapter IV article II paragraph 2 states that the government and local governments are obliged to provide services and facilities and ensure the implementation of quality education for every citizen without discrimination.

Effective and meaningful learning must be in direct contact with students' lives in their environment. Student life in the madrasa environment, family, and community is influenced by internal and external factors that exist in students. These factors include socio-cultural, socio-economic, and existing geographical conditions. This is all an ongoing process.

Along with the advancement of knowledge and technology, socio-cultural and socio-economic life are increasingly unable to be limited by space and time because the life of our society cannot be separated from the life of the international community, which demands increasingly higher human resources.

Meanwhile, the real condition of our education in terms of preparing human resources that can compete globally is insufficient. Moreover, with the development of the era of globalization, especially in the field of information technology, it is necessary to have mastery of ICT, both for students and educators as well as administrative staff, to improve the active, innovative, creative, effective, fun and Islamic learning process.

Attention to quality is very important. In education, quality issues are not only about inputs, processes, and outputs but also outcomes. Quality education inputs are educators, employees, students, curriculum, facilities, infrastructure, and other aspects of education. The process of quality education is the process of learning and providing education. Quality output is graduates who have the required competencies. Moreover, quality outcomes are graduates who can continue to a higher level of education.

The goals of National Education will be realized through two main things: first, through the formation of high-quality and independent human beings. Second, efforts are needed to improve human and material resources. Human resources are one of the most influential factors in the quality of education. These human resources components are in the form of educators and education staff which include: educators, education managers, supervisors, curriculum developers, librarians, laboratory assistants, and resource technicians. Material resources, including the importance of the role of the curriculum by the demands of the times, facilities, infrastructure, the role of parents and society, and the government's commitment to education.

Of course, many things can be done to solve this problem, one of which is the implementation of strategies to improve the quality of education; this customer focus service strategy is the key to success in achieving success in managing education with good management of the education unit will succeed in meeting the demands of quality or quality of appropriate education. with national education standards so that through good management it is expected to produce good quality education.

B. METHODOLOGY

This type of research is descriptive qualitative research with a case study approach to determine the implementation of Total Quality Management (TQM) at MTs Annur 1 Malangbong Garut. used are interviews, observations, and documents.

C. RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Implementation of Total Quality Management (TQM) at MTs Annur 1 Malangbong Garut

MTs Annur 1 Malangbong Garut is a Madrasa with an Islamic character and excels in managing its education system. The services provided by the madrasa can attract the attention of both internal and external education customers, even though MTs Annur 1 Malangbong Garut has the status of a private madrasa. MTs Annur 1 Malangbong Garut, with all its totality, continues to improve and provide opportunities to motivate and fulfill the expectations of madrasa customers (teachers, students, employees, parents, communities, and other education institutions). MTs Annur 1 Malangbong Garut, which has a quality culture, provides services that exceed customer expectations. This can be seen from the conducive madrasa culture, effective teaching and learning process, adequate infrastructure, clear and directed curriculum, and competent educators and education staff.

Along with the growth of the global world, MTs Annur 1 Malangbong Garut continues to carry out self-development and continuous improvement, which is conceptualized in the application of Total Quality Management (TQM).

The initial effort made by MTs Annur 1 Malangbong Garut was to formulate a vision and mission. Based on the vision and mission of the madrasa, the head of the madrasa and all levels of management, through their strategic plans, develop quality policies. The quality policy of MTs Annur 1 Malangbong Garut is as follows:

- a) Education that is strongly committed to graduating students with noble character and optimal academic achievements;
- b) Realizing a globally oriented and competitive education at the world level based on Islamic and national values;
- c) Providing excellent service by prioritizing stakeholder satisfaction;

The commitments described above are realized by:

- a) Standardize Human Resources, systems, and services;
- b) Expanding networks and cooperation with other institutions;
- c) Meet the required requirements.

This commitment is carried out sincerely and continuously to maintain the image of MTs Annur 1 Malangbong Garut as a madrasa worthy of emulation.

About the above quality standards, MTs Annur 1 Malangbong Garut designs and implements a quality assurance strategy. The achievement of these quality standards can be met through educational services. MTs Annur 1 Malangbong Garut in achieving quality education include management services for teachers and employees; management services to students; management services to parents; management services in further education; management services at madrasas as a system; and teacher services to students.

a. Management Services to Internal Customers

Based on the results of the documentation study, it is known that the level of satisfaction of teachers and employees at MTs Annur 1 Malangbong Garut is carried out through the distribution of a questionnaire once a year. Therefore, things that need to be improved by schools related to services to teachers and employees can be realized, and teachers/employees are satisfied with management services. The satisfaction of teachers and employees affects the performance of teachers and employees in serving students.

The forms of management services for MTs Annur 1 Malangbong Garut to teachers and employees are as follows:

1) Empowerment of teachers and employees:

All stakeholders of MTs Annur 1 Malangbong Garut, both teachers, staff, cleaning services, and security guards, are fully involved in achieving the desired educational goals by their respective job descriptions.;

2) Communication :

The forms of communication applied at MTs Annur 1 Malangbong Garut are weekly meetings and home visits. In the home visit activity, the head of the madrasa, together with all teachers and employees, visits the teacher's house every three months in turn with the aim that the relationship between the head of the madrasa, teachers, and all employees becomes more familiar, harmonious and can understand each other.;

3) Motivation :

The form of motivation for teachers and employees of MTs Annur 1 Malangbong Garut is a routine study activity of a group of teachers studying Hadith/interpretation and the opportunity to exchange ideas related to personal and family problems or difficulties in teaching and learning activities.;

4) Education and training:

Increasing the professionalism of employees is carried out through various education and training, namely curriculum workshops by bringing in education experts, spiritual development of teachers and employees, coaching reading the Koran, coaching Arabic and English, coaching early semesters, coaching homerooms such as coaching in task mastery, coaching aspects mentoring and communication.;

5) Rewards and punishments:

The reward given by MTs Annur 1 Malangbong Garut is in the form of salaries and incentives determined by the Annur Garut Islamic Education Foundation.

MTs Annur 1 Malangbong Garut, with its strategic planning, places excellent service as a priority so that it can bring customers, especially teachers and employees, to a high level of satisfaction and loyalty. High levels of teacher and employee satisfaction positively influence the quality of services provided to students.

b. Service Management to Student

Service management of MTs Annur 1 Malangbong Garut on students consist from:

1) Integrative curriculum:

MTs Annur 1 Malangbong curriculum Garut designed as following:

- a) Curriculum typical consist of eye Islamic lessons, Koran, Language, Worship Practical, library and competence-base religious;
- b) Curriculum Ministry of Religion and National Education consists of PKN, IPA/SCIENCE, IPS, Indonesian, Mathematics, and Physical Education. Including curriculum payload local consisting of from Sundanese; _
- c) MTs Annur 1 Malangbong Garut also applies activity extracurricular, i.e., scouting, archery, badminton, tennis table, theater, English Club, Writing Club, karate, football, marching band, and calligraphy.

2) Complete facilities and infrastructure:

Facility facilities and infrastructure provided by MTs Annur 1 Malangbong Garut include:

- a. library. As for service library for students, that is data collection member new, borrowed book, know words, show off words, resume
- b. Facility sports, consists of volleyball, tennis table.
- c. Cooperative and canteen honesty ; and
- d. Parking .

3) Environment good school:

MTs Annur 1 Malangbong environment Garut set as good as possible, so students feel comfortable living there. This thing proven with setting environment neat and clean school, wide madrasa yard, far away from the noise, shady (there are soothing trees) and the environment supportive surroundings services offered.

4) Balanced reward and punishment:

MTs Annur 1 Malangbong Garut apply gift rewards and punishments as a form of motivation to students. Giving appropriate reward and punishment with performance or violation committed Data above show that TQM management is successfully applied at MTs Annur 1 Malangbong Garut. This is what makes the student comfortable and happy at the madrasa so that they can follow the learning process and teach with good. Totality this, in turn push student to boost achievement and virtuous character sublime.

c. Service Management towards parents

MTs Annur 1 Malangbong Garut apply various programs for synergize madrasas and parents via:

- 1) Book liaison. Book liaison the containing activity student (aspect worship, social, and independence);
- 2) Home visits. Activity Home visit MTs Annur 1 Malangbong Garut shaped class teacher visits to house purposeful student _ for weave familiarity between teachers, parents, and students. The teacher can monitor the direct activity of students when at home, and parents could convey by directly related development to students;
- 3) Parenting
- 4) WA group. MTs Annur 1 Malangbong Garut also applies communication through the WA group in Thing this classified on each class;

d. Service Management at madrasas as System

Service management at madrasas as an internal system implementation Total Quality Management MTs Annur 1 Malangbong Garut based on:

- 1) Planning strategic quality. Plan strategic quality no miss from vision, mission, values, madrasa goals, programs, and targets that must be achieved ;
- 2) Cost quality. MTs Annur 1 Malangbong Financing Garut sourced from parents and development _ activities carried out by the foundation.
- 3) Supervision and evaluation of the educational process, namely monitoring and evaluation period short consist of monitoring and evaluation daily as well as weekly. Monitoring and evaluation period long conducted in form supervision. Besides supervision carried out towards the teacher, also supervises guardian class very in a year and supervise coordinator level carried out a year once.

e. Teacher 's Service to Student

Services at MTs Annur 1 Malangbong Garut on students in activity study teach as follows:

1) Planning learning

What the teacher prepares in planning learning is method learning, learning media, teaching materials, reward and punishment, form evaluation and rubric score, as well as remedial ;

2) Learning media

Media used by eye lessons and needs of the student such as learning videos;

3) Method learning

Activity study teaching MTs Annur 1 Malangbong Garut with approach learning contextual, scientific and student center;

4) materials

Based on the curriculum used, namely: the Ministry of Religion, the Education Officer, and the curriculum of the Annur. Foundation Garut.

5) Rewards and punishments

Rewards given _ in the learning process teaching in the classroom, in general, is in the form of praise and opportunity to appear in front of the ranks of teacher's management;

6) Evaluation learning

Evaluation MTs Annur 1 Malangbong lesson Garut held through Mid-Semester Assessment, Assessment End of Semester;

7) Remedial

MTs Annur 1 Malangbong remedial program Garut consists of remedial teaching for individual, group, and peer tutoring and remedial therapy psychological to grow motivation, improve behavior socially, and overcome deviation..

f. Results of Total Quality Management (TQM) at MTs Annur 1 Malangbong Garut

Optimization performance party management together all teachers and employees produce quality results. _ that thing could be proved with MTs Annur 1 Malangbong graduates Garut which have good performance.

D. CONCLUSION

- 1) Total Quality Management is an approach to operating trying effort to maximize competitive power organization through continuously repairing products, services, energy work, processes, and the environment.
- 2) Total Quality Management (TQM) elements include a focus on customers, obsession with quality, scientific approach, long commitment, working with the same team repair system by sustainability, education, training, and freedom of control.
- 3) Principles Total Quality Management (TQM) must build on a base five pillars system, namely, Product, Process, Organization, Leadership, and Commitment.
- 4) There is four difference tree between TQM and method management, including origin intellectual, source innovation, country of origin, and dissemination process or deployment.
- 5) Total Quality Management (TQM) in Development Quality (Quality Improvement) in the world of education is a philosophy about repair by Keep going continuously, which can give set tools practical to every institution of education in Fulfill needs, wants, and expectations of its customers, when this and the future come.
- 6) Success enhancement of the quality of MTs Annur 1 Malangbong Garut through application Total Quality Management no miss from principle customer focus, improvement by continuously, and the total involvement of all stakeholders. MTs Annur 1 Malangbong Garut give the best service based on reliability, power responsiveness, empathy, and certainty (according to Kotler's principle). In planning the strategic location of MTs Annur 1, Malangbong Garut prioritized excellent service so that it could bring customers (especially teachers and employees) a level of satisfaction and high loyalty.

- 7) High teacher and employee satisfaction levels influence the quality of services provided _ to students. Service best teacher to student delivers students in a situation where they feel happy to learn and feel at home in the madrasa so that they can reach performance optimal academic and moral glorious as reflected in madrasa visions and missions. Performance student good academic nor Non-Academic give satisfaction with parents and education continued. Despite thereby amount of obstacles still found, however, with high commitment and work of a reliable team, MTs Annur 1 Malangbong Garut could increase quality by becoming a model of a cultured madrasa quality in the district Garut.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. Al-Jufri, Hamid, Sistem Informasi Manajemen Pendidikan, Jakarta : PT. Smart Grafika, 2011.
2. Arifin, Zainal. Konsep dan Model Pengembangan Kurikulum. Bandung: PT Remaja Rosdakarya, 2014.
3. Arikunto, Suharsimi. Manajemen Pendidikan. Yogyakarta: Aditya Media, 2008.
4. Dedi Mulyasana, Pendidikan Bermutu dan Berdaya Saing, (et. II; Bandung: PT Remaja Rosdakarya, 2012.
5. <http://hefniy.wordpress.com/2008/10/06/aplikasi-tqm-dalam-lembaga-pendidikan/> [http:// Khamim Zarkasih Putro dan M.Mahlani / mahalaniraya.wordpress.com](http://KhamimZarkasihPutro.com) pendekatan-total-quality-management-tqm-dalam-pendidikan
6. <http://weblogask.blogspot.com/2013/03/gerakan-mutu-dalam-pendidikan.html/>
7. Kamus Besar Bahasa Indonesia (KBBI) Versi Online, Online <http://kbbi.web.id/manajemen> (Diakses tanggal 3 Agustus 2019).
8. Keputusan Menteri Agama Nomor 184 Tahun 2019 Tentang Pedoman Implementasi Pada Madrasah.
9. Mulyasa, E.. Kurikulum Berbasis Kompetensi, Strategi dan Implementasi. Bandung: Remaja Rosdakarya, 2003
10. Nasution, Manajemen Mutu Terpadu (Total Quality Management), Cet, II; Bogor: Ghalia Indonesia, 2005.
11. Onisimus Amtu, Manajemen Pendidikan di Era Otonomi Daerah Konsep. Strategi, dan Implementasi, Bandung: Alfabeta, 2011
12. Riyadi, Ahmad Ali dan Fahrurrozi. Manajemen Mutu Terpadu Pendidikan (TQM in Education). Jogjakarta: IRCiSoD, 2010
13. Supardi. Sekolah Efektif: Konsep Dasar dan Praktiknya. Cet. II; Jakarta: RajaGrafindo Persada, 2015
14. Sallis, Edward, Total Quality Management In Education Manajemen Mutu Pendidikan, cetakan ke XIII, Yogyakarta: IRCiSoD, 2011.http://id.wikipedia.org/wiki/Manajemen_kualitas_total
15. Suyadi Prawirosentono, Filosofi Baru tentang Manajemen Mutu Terpadu Abad 21, Jakarta: Bumi Aksara, 2007.
16. Suyatno. Sekolah Dasar Islam Terpadu Dalam Konsepsi Kelas Menengah Muslim Indonesia. Yogyakarta: Universitas Ahmad Dahlan, 2015.
17. Tafsir, Ahmad. Ilmu Pendidikan Dalam Perspektif Islam. Bandung: Remaja Rosda Karya, 2000.
18. Yamin, Moh. Panduan Manajemen Mutu Kurikulum Pendidikan. Yogyakarta: Diva Press, 2012